

μ - β -generalized α -closed sets in generalized topological spaces

Kowsalya M

MSc Mathematics, Avinashilingam University,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Jayanthi D

Assistant Professor of Mathematics, Avinashilingam
University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we have introduced a new class of sets in generalized topological spaces called μ - β -generalized α -closed sets. Also we have investigated some of their basic properties.

Keywords: Generalized topology, generalized topological spaces, μ - α -closed sets, μ - β -generalized α -closed sets.

1. Introduction

The concept of generalized topological spaces is introduced by A. Csaszar [1] in 2002. He also introduced many μ -closed sets like μ -semi closed sets, μ -pre closed sets, μ - β -closed sets, μ - α -closed sets, μ -regular closed sets etc., in generalized topological spaces. In 2016 Srija. S and Jayanthi. D [4] introduced g_μ -semi closed set in generalized topological spaces. In this paper, we have introduced a new class of sets in generalized topological spaces called μ - β -generalized α -closed sets. Also we have investigated some of their basic properties and produced many interesting theorems.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1: [1] Let X be a nonempty set. A collection μ of subsets of X is a generalized topology (or briefly GT) on X if it satisfies the following:

- i. $\emptyset, X \in \mu$ and
- ii. If $\{M_i: i \in I\} \subseteq \mu$, then $\bigcup_{i \in I} M_i \in \mu$

If μ is a GT on X , then (X, μ) is called a generalized topological space (or briefly GTS), and the elements of μ are called μ -open sets and their complement are called μ -closed sets.

Definition 2.2: [1] Let (X, μ) be a GTS and let $A \subseteq X$. Then μ -closure of A , denoted by $c_\mu(A)$, is the intersection of all μ -closed sets containing A .

Definition 2.3: [1] Let (X, μ) be a GTS and let $A \subseteq X$. Then μ -interior of A , denoted by $i_\mu(A)$, is the union of all μ -open sets contained in A .

Definition 2.4: [1] Let (X, μ) be a GTS. A subset A of X is said to be

- i. μ -semi-closed if $i_\mu(c_\mu(A)) \subseteq A$
- ii. μ -pre-closed if $c_\mu(i_\mu(A)) \subseteq A$
- iii. μ - α -closed if $c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(A))) \subseteq A$
- iv. μ - β -closed if $i_\mu(c_\mu(i_\mu(A))) \subseteq A$
- v. μ -regular closed if $A = c_\mu(i_\mu(A))$

Definition 2.5: [3] Let (X, μ) be a GTS. A subset A of X is said to be

- i. μ -regular generalized closed if $c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$, where U is μ -regular open in X ,
- ii. μ -generalized closed set if $c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$, and U is μ -open in X ,
- iii. μ -generalized α -closed set if $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$, and U is μ -open in X .

The complement of μ -semi-closed (respectively μ -pre-closed, μ - α -closed, μ - β -closed, μ -regular closed, etc.,) is called μ -semi-open (respectively μ -pre-open, μ - α -open, μ - β -open, μ -regular open, etc.,) in X .

3. μ - β -generalized α -closed sets in generalized topological spaces

In this section we have introduced μ - β -generalized α -closed sets in generalized topological spaces and studied some of their basic properties.

Definition 3.1: A subset A of a GTS (X, μ) is called a μ - β -generalized α -closed set (briefly μ - β G α CS) if $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is μ - β -open in X .

Example 3.2: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, μ) is a GTS. Now μ - β O(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.3: Every μ -closed set in (X, μ) is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) but not conversely.

Proof: Let A be a μ -closed set in (X, μ) then $c_\mu(A) = A$. Now let $A \subseteq U$ where U is μ - β -open in (X, μ) . Then $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq c_\mu(A) = A \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Therefore $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$. This implies, A is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Example 3.4: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and let $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then (X, μ) is a GTS. Now μ - β O(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, d\}, \{b, c\}, \{c, d\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{b, c, d\}, \{a, c, d\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{d\}$ is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) , but not a μ -closed set as $c_\mu(A) = c_\mu(\{d\}) = \{b, d\} \neq A$.

Theorem 3.5: Every μ - α -closed set in (X, μ) is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Proof: Let A be a μ - α -closed in (X, μ) , then $c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(A))) \subseteq A$. Now let $A \subseteq U$ where U is μ - β -open in (X, μ) . Then $\alpha c_\mu(A) = A \cup c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(A))) = A \cup A = A \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Therefore $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$ and hence A is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.6: Every μ -regular closed set in (X, μ) is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) but not conversely.

Proof: Let A be a μ -regular closed set in (X, μ) , then $c_\mu(i_\mu(A)) = A$. Now let $A \subseteq U$ where U is a μ - β -open

set in (X, μ) . Then $\alpha c_\mu(A) = A \cup c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(A))) = A \cup c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(c_\mu(i_\mu(A)))))) = A \cup c_\mu(i_\mu(c_\mu(i_\mu(A)))) = A \cup c_\mu(i_\mu(A)) = A \subseteq U$, by hypothesis. Therefore $\alpha c_\mu(A) \subseteq U$. This implies, A is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Example 3.7: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, μ) is a GTS. Now μ - β O(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{c\}$ is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) , but not a μ -regular closed set as $c_\mu(i_\mu(A)) = c_\mu(i_\mu(\{c\})) = \emptyset \neq A$.

Remark 3.8: A μ -pre-closed is not a μ - β -G α CS in (X, μ) in general.

Example 3.9: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, μ) is a GTS. Now μ - β O(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is a μ -pre-closed in (X, μ) as $c_\mu(i_\mu(A)) = c_\mu(i_\mu(\{a\})) = \emptyset \subseteq A$, but not a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) as $\alpha c_\mu(A) = X \not\subseteq \{a, b\} = U$.

Remark 3.10: A μ - β -closed is not a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) in general.

Example 3.11: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mu = \{\emptyset, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, μ) is a GTS. Now μ - β O(X) = $\{\emptyset, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, \{b, c\}, \{a, c\}, X\}$. Then $A = \{a\}$ is a μ - β -closed in (X, μ) as $i_\mu(c_\mu(i_\mu(A))) = i_\mu(c_\mu(i_\mu(\{a\}))) = \emptyset \subseteq A$, but not a μ - β G α CS as in Example 3.9.

In the following diagram, we have provided relations between various types of closed sets.

Theorem 3.12: Let A and B be μ - β G α CSs in (X, μ) such that $c_\mu(A) = \alpha c_\mu(A)$ and $c_\mu(B) = \alpha c_\mu(B)$, then $A \cup B$ is a μ - β G α CS in (X, μ) .

Proof: Let $A \cup B \subseteq U$, where U is a μ - β -open set in X . Then $A \subseteq U$ and $B \subseteq U$. since A and B are μ -

$\beta G\alpha CS$, $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$ and $\alpha_{\mu}(B) \subseteq U$. Now, $\alpha_{\mu}(A \cup B) \subseteq c_{\mu}(A \cup B) = c_{\mu}(A) \cup c_{\mu}(B) = \alpha_{\mu}(A) \cup \alpha_{\mu}(B) \subseteq U \cup U = U$. Hence, $A \cup B$ is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.13: If a subset A of X is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ and $A \subseteq B \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A)$, then B is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X .

Proof: Let A be a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ such that $A \subseteq B \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A)$. Suppose U is a μ - β -open set of X such that $B \subseteq U$, by assumption, we have $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$ as $A \subseteq B \subseteq U$. Now $\alpha_{\mu}(B) \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(\alpha_{\mu}(A)) = \alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$. That is $\alpha_{\mu}(B) \subseteq U$. Therefore, B is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X .

Theorem 3.14: In a GTS X , for each $x \in X$, $\{x\}$ is μ - β -closed or its complement $X - \{x\}$ is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in (X, μ) .

Proof: Suppose that $\{x\}$ is not a μ - β -closed set in (X, μ) . Then $X - \{x\}$ is not a μ - β -open set in (X, μ) . The only μ - β -open set containing $X - \{x\}$ is X . Thus $X - \{x\} \subseteq X$ and so $\alpha_{\mu}(X - \{x\}) \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(X) = X$. Therefore $\alpha_{\mu}(X - \{x\}) \subseteq X$ and so $X - \{x\}$ is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.15: If A is both a μ - β -open set and μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in (X, μ) , then A is a μ - α -closed set.

Proof: Let A be a μ - β -open set and μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in (X, μ) . Then, $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq A$ as $A \subseteq A$. we have $A \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A)$. Therefore, $A = \alpha_{\mu}(A)$. Hence A is a μ - α -closed set in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.16: Every subset of X is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X iff every μ - β -open set in X is μ - α -closed in X .

Proof: Necessity: Let A be a μ - β -open set in X and by hypothesis, A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X . Hence by Theorem 3.15, A is a μ - α -closed set in X .

Sufficiency: Let A be a subset of X and U be a μ - β -open set such that $A \subseteq U$, then by hypothesis, U is μ - α -closed. This implies that $\alpha_{\mu}(U) = U$ and $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(U) = U$. Hence $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$. Thus A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ set in (X, μ) .

Theorem 3.17: A subset A of X is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ if and only if $\alpha_{\mu}(A) - A$ contains no non-empty μ - β -closed set in X .

Proof: Let A be a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X . Suppose F is a non-empty μ - β -closed set such that $F \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A) - A$.

Then $F \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A) \cap A^c$. Therefore $F \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A)$ and $F \subseteq A^c$. This implies $A \subseteq F^c$. Since F^c is a μ - β -open set, by definition of μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$, $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq F^c$. That is $F \subseteq (\alpha_{\mu}(A))^c$. Hence $F \subseteq \alpha_{\mu}(A) \cap (\alpha_{\mu}(A))^c = \emptyset$. That is $F = \emptyset$, which is a contradiction. Thus $\alpha_{\mu}(A) - A$ contains no non-empty μ - β -closed set in X .

Conversely, assume that $\alpha_{\mu}(A) - A$ contains no non-empty μ - β -closed set in X . Let $A \subseteq U$, where U is a μ - β -open set in X . Suppose that $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \not\subseteq U$, then $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \cap U^c$ is a non-empty closed subset of $\alpha_{\mu}(A) - A$, which is a contradiction. Therefore $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$ and hence A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X .

Theorem 3.18: If $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$ and A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X , then A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ relative to Y .

Proof: Given that $A \subseteq Y \subseteq X$ and A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ in X . Let $A \subseteq Y \cap U$, where U is μ - β -open set in X . since A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$, $A \subseteq U$ implies $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq U$. This implies $Y \cap \alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq Y \cap U$ and $\alpha_{\mu}(A) \subseteq Y \cap U$. That is A is a μ - $\beta G\alpha CS$ relative to Y .

REFERENCES

1. Csarzar, A., Generalized open sets in generalized topologies, Acta Mathematica Hungar., 96(2002), 351-357.
2. Csarzar, A., Generalized open sets in generalized topologies, Acta Mathematica Hungar., 106(2005), 53-66.
3. Fritzie Mae Vasquez Valenzuela and Helen moso Rara., μ -rgb-sets in a generalized topological spaces, International Journal of Mathematical Analysis-vol-8, 2014, 1791-1797.
4. Srija, s, and Jayanthi, D., g_{μ} - semi closed set in generalized topological spaces, International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Application Science (IJSEAS)-volume-2, issue-4, April 2016, 292-294.